

Bridge damage characterisation using machine learning: methods and advances

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Abstract

Bridge deflection is a descriptive proxy for potential bridge deterioration and damage. It can be used to determine bridge condition and link this to actionable damage states for timely and accurate damage mitigation and adaptation. While design guidelines mandate strict deflection control at the design stage, primarily for serviceability, there are currently no assessment guidelines or available framework to facilitate bridge damage identification based on bridge deck deflections. A thorough review of the literature revealed that the main reason that deflection is not used as a damage proxy is the complex mechanics underlying its development. A state-of-the-art review is presented to efficiently characterise global bridge damage related to deck deflections. The approach goes beyond existing methods by striving to reveal the causes of bridge deck deflection and their interdependencies, offering a clearer understanding and interpretation of the factors driving this phenomenon. Given the significant uncertainties around deflection causes and the impracticality of complex, tedious analyses for large bridge portfolios, Machine Learning (ML) is proposed as a scalable solution that reduces modelling effort, enhances explainability, and can successfully correlate deflections with damage levels. It then proposes a conceptual Physics-Based ML approach that correlates deflection patterns with actionable damage states, offering a roadmap for future research to enhance bridge damage characterisation. Unlike prior studies, it integrates all major deterioration mechanisms and their interactions into a unified deflection analysis.

Keywords: deflection; bridge; damage characterisation; Machine Learning; actionable damage states

Graphical abstract

Highlights

- Identification of critical research gaps in using deflection as a global damage characterisation for bridges
- First comprehensive review of bridge deflections accounting for all critical deterioration mechanisms and their interactions.
- Conceptual framework that incorporates rigorous alignment of measured bridge deflections with model predictions incorporating creep and shrinkage, improving damage characterisation accuracy
- Physics-Based approach to correlate deflection patterns to specific damage states

1. Introduction

Bridges are primary components of transportation networks, providing essential services that underpin economic activity worldwide ([Frangopol et al., 2017](#); [Lee et al., 2022](#)). As essential parts of highway infrastructure, they have been increasingly exposed to multiple hazards throughout their life cycle, making safety problems a growing public concern ([Andrić and Lu, 2016](#); [Subbiah et al., 2025](#)). Factors like ageing, environmental stressors, rising traffic demands and loads threaten their structural integrity ([Abarca, 2022](#); [Principi et al., 2024](#)). Bridge failures can have catastrophic consequences, threatening human life, damaging infrastructure, disrupting economies, and eroding public trust and social cohesion. Recent disasters have exposed the fragility of infrastructure in Europe. Greece endured its worst wildfires, followed by Storm Daniel's catastrophic floods, which caused multiple bridge collapses, particularly in Thessaly ([Kougkoulos et al., 2024](#)). Slovenia faced its most severe floods in August 2023, crippling over 65% of the country ([Argyroudis and Mitoulis, 2021](#); [Liu and Xiang, 2024](#)). These events follow Italy's Polcevera Viaduct (Morandi Bridge) collapse due to corrosion, the replacement of which will exceed € 200 million. As of January 2024, Ukraine reported damage or destruction to 304 bridges and bridge crossings, amounting to \$155 billion in losses ([KSE, 2024](#)).

To ensure bridge safety and longevity, proactive monitoring and maintenance are essential, with an emphasis on early damage detection and timely interventions ([Achillopoulou et al., 2020](#)). Conventional bridge damage assessment techniques, based on visual inspection and numerical structural analysis, require substantial time and resources, while frequently miss latent defects and early damage indicators, for example deflections. Modern civil engineering increasingly employs Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) systems to quantitatively evaluate and track bridge structural integrity in real-time ([Abouhamad et al., 2017](#); [Sacks et al., 2020](#)). However, correlating health monitoring data with structural model response parameters of an asset to characterise its damage levels is essential to enable timely decision-making and adaptation planning ([Gatti, 2019](#)). This challenge is particularly acute given the massive volumes of complex, uncertain and noisy data

generated by modern SHM systems. ML is emerging as a promising tool for bridge damage characterisation, offering rapid and accurate processing and interpretation of big data, identifying meaningful patterns and anomalies, and establishing quantitative relationships between sensor measurements and actionable damage states ([Fan et al., 2021](#)).

Despite the well-recognised importance of deflection in evaluating bridge conditions, there is still a lack of guidelines connecting deflection measurements to specific damage states likely due to the convoluted nature of deflections. Our study intends to fill this gap by investigating the convolutions associated with such bridge deflection and ultimately link those to damage states of concrete bridges. The latter arises from a range of factors, that pose a multifaceted challenge in accurately evaluating its implication on structural integrity, particularly in ageing bridge infrastructure.

While deflections are typically expected to result from loading, they can also be influenced by numerous linear and non-linear phenomena. This includes short-term effects such as cracking, corrosion of tendons and reinforcement rebars, as well as chronic, long-term effects such as creep, shrinkage, load redistribution, foundation defects, settlements, and overloading ([Jun et al., 2007](#); [Domaneshi et al., 2020](#); [Markogiannaki et al., 2022](#)). The complexity of the mechanics of deflection makes it an uncertain metric for deterioration, particularly in older bridges where predicting deflection-related damage is exceedingly difficult ([Izonin et al., 2024](#)).

Nevertheless, deflection remains a key macroscopic indicator of bridge deterioration, often providing a reliable link to underlying structural damage. Moreover, it is a critical metric that can be directly and accurately measured using physical sensors, point cloud data, or satellite imagery, enabling comprehensive bridge health assessments. Variations in deflection and bridge geometry, particularly when compared to baseline measurements, serve as early warning signs of structural weaknesses or progressive deterioration ([Domaneshi et al., 2023](#)). The capability to monitor deflection through remote sensing offers a quantifiable, real-time indicator of a bridge's condition, facilitating timely maintenance and repair interventions.

Considerable research effort has been devoted to investigating damage characterisation using bridge dynamic properties including natural frequencies, mode shapes, and damping ratios obtained from vehicle-bridge interactions ([Huth et al., 2005](#); [Chatzi and Fuggini, 2015](#)). However, these modal parameters often demonstrate limited sensitivity to localised damage, while physical inspections may be impractical due to structural vulnerability or safety concerns, necessitating continuous long-term monitoring ([Liu et al., 2023](#)). In practice, deflection measurements frequently provide a reliable, cost effective and quantifiable indicator of structural deterioration, offering a clearer assessment of a bridge's degraded state.

One of the most promising yet underexplored cutting-edge approaches is the use of ML algorithms to facilitate bridge global damage identification exploiting bridge deck deflections ([Kazantzi et al., 2024](#)). This approach has received limited attention, stemming from a disconnect between practitioners and researchers: engineers who could utilise deflection data to assess bridge damage are not yet adopting ML techniques due to a lack of streamlined tools, while scientists developing ML models do not fully understand the complex nature of bridge deflections and the needs of bridge owners and operators. While the use of ML in bridge monitoring is growing and several past studies have applied ML to structural performance assessment and damage detection, only a limited number of studies have specifically focused on linking permanent deflection to specific damage states in bridges. [Kazantzi et al., 2024](#) and [Izonin et al., 2024](#) have attempted to establish a relationship between bridge deflection and damage states in concrete bridges whilst employing ML as an analytical tool to process and support the decoding of complex deflection patterns. Nevertheless, those studies have some limitations attributable to the following aspects: (i) they only focus on corrosion as the main form of damage, missing other important factors that affect concrete bridges over time. Specifically, they do not account for creep and shrinkage which are two fundamental processes that significantly influence how concrete structures deflect and perform throughout their lifespan, (ii) they neglect to align measured deflections with model predictions. This oversight prevents validation against real structural behaviour and compromises accurate damage assessment,

(ii) they follow a data-driven approach with no known physical laws accounted for into the ML training process.

This paper proposes a conceptual framework to facilitate well-informed and effective bridge damage assessment by making three fundamental advances that distinguish it from previous research. Firstly, it establishes rigorous alignment of measured deflections with model predictions. Secondly, it introduces the first comprehensive analysis of bridge deflections that simultaneously accounts for all critical deterioration mechanisms, including creep, shrinkage, corrosion, and cracking along with their complex interactions. Thirdly, it proposes a Physics-Based approach that correlates deflection patterns with damage states. usually characterised in fragility studies ([Argyroudis et al., 2019](#); [Argyroudis and Mitoulis, 2021](#)).

In Section 1, we present the key challenges in the field of bridge damage characterisation, review existing approaches and the potential of ML, identify critical knowledge gaps, and highlight the novel contributions of this research. Section 2 sets out the methodology of the review conducted explaining the papers selection process. In Section 3, factors that influence deflection are thoroughly investigated subsequently. The characteristics of each causal factor and its impact on deflection are explained. The review highlights the complexity of factors affecting deflection and, despite its potential in this challenging domain, finds that only few studies have employed ML to predict bridge deflection based on specific causes, and even fewer have examined its connection to bridge damage states. In Section 4, we introduce our philosophy for integrating ML and AI in bridge engineering. In particular, we focus on the challenges and methodologies for assessing bridge damage through deflection. The limitations of traditional methods, e.g. FEM and the potential of ML to analyse large datasets for quicker and more accurate damage assessments is also highlighted. The paper concludes with a conceptual and practical framework that introduces bridge deck deflection as a proxy for global bridge damage characterisation to facilitate decision making.

2. Methodology for the selection of published research papers

The review followed a systematic process comprising three key steps: (1) formulating search strings, (2) conducting searches in the Scopus database, and (3) evaluating the articles retrieved. The paper selection process for Sections 1 and 3, is shown in detail in Figure 1. Step 1 involved developing the search string, which was structured as follows: “concrete bridge” AND “deflection” OR “displacement”. After formulating the search string in Step 1, a Scopus search for the defined string within the 'Article Title, Keywords, and Abstract' fields initially resulted in 7,426 papers (Step 2.1). Scopus database was used for paper selection as it is one of the most trusted databases for high-quality, peer-reviewed research. Since Scopus applies strict indexing criteria, it helps filter out low-quality or non-peer-reviewed papers, making the selection process rigorous ([Falagas et al., 2007](#)). In Step 2.2, the retrieved papers were then sorted by relevance and filtered to 5,226, focusing exclusively on engineering-related studies and English-language publications. The approach followed in Steps 2.1 and 2.2 aligns with Scopus's relevance policy ([Elsevier, 2025](#)), where specific factors contribute to the ranking score: (i) number of hits, (ii) significance of a word, (iii) position of a word, (iv) location of a word, (v) proximity and (vi) completeness. The frequency of a term's appearance is essential, as more frequent occurrences suggest greater relevance to the document's topic. Not all terms carry the same weight; commonly used words score lower in significance than more unusual terms. Scopus employs Term Frequency/Inverse Document Frequency (TF/IDF) to assign a weight to each term based on its occurrence across all documents, enhancing the ranking of less common words that provide specific insight. The location of a term also matters with terms in titles, abstracts, or keywords hold more importance than those in references. The placement of a term's first occurrence adds weight, with earlier appearances indicating higher relevance. Additionally, terms that appear close together in a document and queries where all words appear in the same field contribute to a higher relevance score.

Figure 1: Selection process showing the number of papers progressively excluded in each step, using a total of seven context-specific criteria to narrow down the number of papers from 7,426 to 120.

An initial screening was conducted in Step 2.3 by reviewing titles, abstracts and keywords revealing key causes of bridge deflection, including creep, shrinkage, tendon corrosion, concrete cracking, traffic loads, fatigue, dynamic effects and soil settlements. In Step 2.4 a refined search for each cause was then performed by adding the specific cause to the original search string. A total of 2274 papers focused on the causes of deck deflection in concrete bridges, while the remaining studies were unrelated, as they examined different materials or structural components. In Step 2.5, journal articles

and conference papers published before 2020 with fewer than 6 citations and no influence on policies were excluded, prioritising studies of greater influence and impact. This citation-based criterion was applied only after relevance-based screening, not at the beginning of the process. Importantly, peer-reviewed journal articles were retained regardless of citation count if deemed contextually significant. This selection criterion ensured the inclusion of works that have achieved significant academic recognition and helped prioritise influential, high-quality literature without omitting recent or emerging work. Cracking, creep, shrinkage and corrosion emerged as the most commonly studied factors in bridges, with dynamic effects, fatigue and settlements being the least examined resulting in a total of 2155 papers at the end of Step 2.5. As a result of this, and as further explained in Section 3, causes such as dynamic effects, fatigue and settlements are excluded from this review. Furthermore, causes of bridge deflection are not uncorrelated. Hence, for example, cracking and corrosion or similarly creep and shrinkage might be examined by the same paper. Figure 2 illustrates these interconnections by depicting and explaining the relationships among the deflection causes under investigation. A brief description of the figure is subsequently provided.

Figure 2: The figure shows interconnections between causes of deflection highlighting a complex system of degradation mechanisms in concrete. The direction of the arrows shows unilateral and

bilateral interdependencies which are likely to influence diverse causes of deflection. In addition to these relationships, the figure also displays the number of research papers associated with each cause.

Causes of bridge deck deflection can be divided into independent, interdependent, direct and indirect. Independent causes are those that contribute to deflection on their own, without being influenced by or influencing other causes. Interdependent causes are the ones that bidirectionally influence or amplify each other and are shown with a bidirectional solid blue line in Figure 2. For example, cracking can exacerbate corrosion by exposing the rebar to environmental factors. At the same time, cracking occurs when an expansive layer of corrosion products forms near the interface between the concrete and reinforcement (Aldella et al., 2022). Direct causes, shown with a unidirectional solid green line in Figure 2, occur when one factor immediately leads to or triggers another. For example, overloading leads to cracking in bridge structures due to excessive tensile stresses and material limits being surpassed (Zhu et al., 2022). Finally, indirect causes (unidirectional orange dotted line in Figure 2) occur when one factor contributes to another over time or through intermediate processes. For example, creep-induced deflection might alter a bridge's stiffness, indirectly affecting its response to dynamic loads, but neither process directly initiates nor accelerates the other (Ma et al., 2015).

Progressing with the paper selection, in Step 2.6, the Mendeley Reference Manager application was employed to identify duplicate papers, serving two primary purposes: first to streamline the final review process by ensuring each paper was read only once and second, to highlight studies addressing multiple interdependent factors. This was particularly relevant for studies examining creep-shrinkage, as well as those exploring the combined effects of cracking, creep, and shrinkage. In Step 3.1, the 1256 retrieved papers from the previous step underwent an initial assessment through a detailed and critical review of their abstracts and conclusions. This process excluded studies that were not focused on concrete bridges and did not explicitly address deflection mechanisms, resulting in 502 papers identified as potentially relevant. The 502 papers deemed potentially relevant were subsequently reviewed in full in Step 3.2 to verify their alignment with the research topic. This was achieved by

reviewing papers that address the complexities and uncertainties of bridge deck deflection, tackling the challenges of predicting deflection over long service periods and linking it to actionable bridge damage states. This step further refined the 502 previously selected by applying quality and relevance checks, prioritising peer-reviewed journal articles with strong methodological rigour and direct relevance to the review's objectives. A total of 120 papers were ultimately selected and fully employed in this study, with 22 of them referenced in Section 1 and the remaining used in Section 3.

In Section 4, a Scopus search using the terms “concrete bridge,” “Machine Learning,” “Damage,” and “deflection” or “displacement” identified 14 papers, with two aiming at bridge damage characterisation. Following the paper selection process presented for Section 3, with the exception of Step 2.4 that is not needed in this Section, 2 relevant papers were selected. Moreover, a broader search was conducted using the terms “concrete bridge” along with PINN and Cascade Ensemble. A total of 21 papers were selected following the same methodology. These findings reveal a critical research gap in using deflection as a global damage indicator for bridges and establishing its relationship with specific damage states, particularly through ML-based detection methods.

3. Review of primary deflection mechanisms and associated ML-based detection methods

This section examines the primary causes of bridge deck deflections, emphasising studies that utilise ML techniques to correlate these causes with specific damage states in bridge structures.

Given the complex nature of the development of deflection, analysing the factors that contribute to each cause of deflection can assist engineers to interpret these causes into data for damage characterisation. ML can identify patterns within the data, offering rational explanations of observed deflections and behaviour and the corresponding level of damage.

To manage and limit deflections, design guidelines provide specific thresholds for the slenderness of the beam and/or decks, i.e. depth/length or length/depth or deflection/length. These span limitations ensure that the deflection remains within acceptable limits, ensuring the serviceability of buildings

and bridges under various loads. The bar chart below (Figure 3) compares deflection criteria adopted by some of the International Design Codes presented as a fraction of the span.

Figure 3: Allowable normalised deflection (d) over deck length (L) limits in different international design guidelines

Eurocode 2 ([EN 1992-1-1, 2004](#)) in Section 7.4.1 specifies a general deflection limit of span/250 while in the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) Bridge Design Specification ([AASHTO, 2010](#)) in Section 2.5.2.6.2 are specified limits for various load types, vehicular (veh in the chart) and pedestrian (ped in the chart), ranging from span/1000 for general structures to span/300 for cantilever structures. Similarly, the Chinese standard GB 50010-2010 (Code for Design of Concrete Structures) ([GB 50010, 2015](#)) in Section 3.4.3 outlines deflection limits based on bridge type with L/800 for simply supported spans and L/450 for cantilevers. Differently, no limits are specified in the Australian Standard AS 5100-2 ([Standards Australia International, 2004](#)), in the German DIN (Deutsche Institut für Normung e.V.) 1045-1 ([DIN 1045-1, 2008](#)) and the Standard Specifications for Concrete Structures published by the Japan Society of Civil Engineers ([JSCE, 2007](#)) where only requirements are to ensure that deflections do not impair the structure's functionality, durability, or aesthetics.

However, these simple checks do not take into account the intricate nature of deflection. Historical incidents, such as the 1985 collapse of the Ynys-y-Gwas bridge in the UK ([Al-Mosawe et al., 2022](#)),

the collapse of the Koror-Badeldaob Bridge in Palau in 1996 ([Bažant, et al., 2011](#)), the Polcevera Bridge (Morandi Bridge) in 2018 ([Invernizzi et al., 2022](#)), or the more recent Carola Bridge Dresden partial collapse in September 2024 ([Value.Space, 2024](#)), have demonstrated that excessive deflection and deck displacements can signal structural damage, potentially leading to partial or total failures in bridge structures.

Bridge deflection has normally been used as a response of the bridge deck to load testing ([Alampalli et al., 2021](#)). Several applications of bridge load testing can be found in the literature ([Coletti et al., 2002](#); [Shenton et al., 2007](#); [Li et al., 2013](#); [Cortez et al., 2015](#); [Nilimaa et al., 2015](#); [Lantsoght et al., 2017](#)). Furthermore, research efforts have focused on developing damage identification methods that utilise modal properties of bridges, such as natural frequencies, mode shapes, and modal damping, and vibration and acceleration data obtained from the interaction of passing vehicles and bridge structures, through FE model updating ([Maeck and Roeck, 2003](#); [Huth et al., 2005](#); [Reynders and Roeck, 2009](#); [Ferrari et al., 2019](#); [Yang et al., 2022](#);) However, modal identification does not always correspond to responses in the vertical direction ([An et al., 2019](#)). In response to this, researchers have focused on employing computationally efficient meta (surrogate) models ([Freitag et al., 2015](#)) capable of processing vast amounts of data recorded from traffic loading for complex structures such as bridges ([Akintunde et al., 2021](#); [Deng et al., 2022](#); [Wu and Zhang, 2023](#); [Yessoufou and Zhu, 2023](#); [Bayane et al., 2024](#); [Zhou et al., 2024](#)).

Nevertheless, prestressed concrete bridges are particularly vulnerable to deterioration mechanisms resulting from long-term material effects such as creep, shrinkage, cracking, and tendon corrosion ([Domaneschi et al., 2023](#)). Environmental factors exacerbate degradation, with climate change accelerating the process by reducing material strength ([Nasr et al., 2019](#)). Additionally, elevated CO₂ levels lead to carbonation-induced corrosion, where CO₂ reacts with calcium hydroxide, reducing concrete alkalinity and causing steel reinforcement corrosion ([Lau and Lasa, 2023](#); [Stewart et al., 2011](#)). This ultimately weakens tendon prestressing, crucial for controlling deflections in long-span bridges ([Liu et al., 2015](#)). All these long-term mechanisms manifest themselves through large

deflections at midspans of continuous decks of incrementally launched superstructures or at free ends of box girders in balanced cantilevered bridges. Deflection is a metric of serviceability performance but is not considered to be relevant to ultimate or strength limit states, thus is not relevant to the bearing capacity of the deck at the design stage; however, for existing and aged bridges, deflection, as a response metric, either transient or permanent, is related to the deck stiffness and strength, and past events showed that excessive deflection and deck displacement are a proof of damage, and it can lead to local, partial and global failures of bridges ([Křístek et al., 2006](#)). An evolving and increasing deflection is evidence of deterioration or exceedance of load bearing capacity of the deck superstructure. Given the complexity of deflection behaviour in prestressed concrete bridges ([Barthélémy et al. 2015](#)), where deflections are influenced by a range of complex interconnected factors such as tendon corrosion, concrete creep, shrinkage and cracking, conventional methods often fall short in capturing the full scope of these interdependencies ([Bonopera and Chang, 2020](#); [Jia et al. 2023](#)). ML, particularly through advanced techniques like two-level cascade ensembles of artificial neural networks, can interpret the interconnected nature of factors leading to deflection ([Izonin et al., 2024](#)). Given that cracking, creep, shrinkage, and corrosion emerge as key deterioration mechanisms in bridges, this section focuses on their role as primary drivers of deflection, exploring their complexities and understanding their interactions for improved bridge damage characterisation. Causes like settlements, fatigue and dynamic effects are eccentric compared to the dominant cause mentioned above, therefore are not directly considered in this review. Loading has typically been associated with deflection and studies have already been conducted in this area. Jia

3.1. Creep, shrinkage and other secondary effects are not always accounted for in maintenance

Creep and shrinkage of concrete are two interrelated phenomena that can lead to excessive long-term deflection in concrete members, particularly in prestressed concrete structures ([Chiu et al., 1996](#); [Purba et al., 2023](#)). Both factors have a fundamental impact on the deflection, internal stresses, and overall performance of the bridge over time. The long-term effects of creep and shrinkage are

particularly critical, as they directly influence the structural integrity and serviceability of the bridge, especially for large-span concrete structures ([Dey et al., 2021](#); [Maldar et al., 2024](#); [Gong et al., 2024](#)). Creep is a key factor affecting the long-term performance of concrete structures, particularly in prestressed concrete, as it causes a reduction in prestressing force due to the continued shortening of compressed concrete over time ([Robertson, 2005](#)). This time-dependent deformation leads to changes in the structure, including a reduction in Young's modulus and altered behaviour upon cracking ([Bažant, et al., 2010](#)). Young's modulus decreases as microstructural rearrangement and microcracking occur under sustained load, reducing the concrete's stiffness ([Bažant et al., 2011](#)). Factors influencing creep include water/cement content, relative humidity, temperature, aggregate content, member size, and the concrete's maturity at the time of loading ([Bažant et al., 2012](#)). Creep is also influenced by the maturity of the concrete when the load is first applied and depends on the duration and magnitude of the loading ([Bažant et al., 2011](#)).

Despite codes taking creep into account, albeit in second order analysis, an obsolete standard recommendation for creep design was revealed to be the main cause of the collapse of the Koror-Badeldaob Bridge in Palau ([Yu et al., 2012](#)). After 18 years, the midspan deflection of the bridge reached 1.39 m, prompting the addition of external prestressing and removal of the mid-span hinge. However, it collapsed three months after reopening. The failure was linked to inadequate creep and shrinkage predictions ([Bažant et al., 2012](#)). In fact, [Bažant and Hubler \(2014\)](#) showed that conventional models like ACI, CEB, and JSCE underestimated deflections, while the B3 model, which took into account a larger number of influential concrete parameters, offered better predictions. Yet, given the complexity of accurately predicting creep values, some studies in the literature utilised ML, in particular neural networks, to predict deflections caused by creep (amongst other parameters). [Yong et al. \(2023\)](#) developed a method to predict long-term deflection in prestressed concrete girder bridges using FEM and artificial neural networks (ANN). They created a database of 20 bridge models to analyse structural responses under varying design parameters, incorporating different creep calculation methods, with the ANN predicting deflection-span ratio differences from nine input

variables. Similarly, [Tong et al. \(2024\)](#) introduced a surrogate modelling approach combining LSTM neural networks and PCA for long-term performance predictions of prestressed concrete bridges. Key factors such as creep, shrinkage, and cracking were simulated, with the model predicting mid-span deflection and prestressing loss. [Zhu et al., \(2024\)](#) developed a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) model to predict long-term deflection in concrete bridges. The model uses FE analysis for training data and Principal Component Analysis (PCA) to identify key input variables such as cement type and environmental conditions. It accurately predicts creep and shrinkage strain, and its performance was validated against real deflection data. However, these studies do not address the need to correlate the effects of creep and shrinkage with actionable damage states in bridges for the purpose of bridge damage characterisation and restoration.

3.2 Tendon corrosion and impact on deflection not covered by maintenance manuals

The relationship between corrosion and deflection in post-tensioned and prestressed concrete beams is crucial for understanding their long-term performance ([Granata and La Mendola, 2021](#); [Messina and Proverbio, 2022](#)). At the early days of bridge service life, corrosion has minimal impact on the deck stiffness, but once cracks form, it significantly reduces post-cracking stiffness and alters deflection patterns ([Zhang et al., 2017](#); [He et al., 2021](#)). As corrosion progresses, bridge decks show reduced load-bearing capacity and diversity in failure modes, especially in half-joint concrete bridges ([Pillai et al., 2014](#); [Rosso et al., 2022](#); [Li et al., 2024](#)). Corrosion of bridge tendons, worsened by moisture and chloride ingress, weakens their tensile capacity, leading to visible deflections and complicates structural assessments ([CS455, 2022](#); [Kazantzi et al., 2024](#)). Prestressing loss due to corrosion of tendons is a scenario that has occurred on several bridges, e.g., the [Polyfytos Bridge](#) resulting in excessive cantilever deflections (Figure 4).

Figure 4: Snapshots of the Polyfytos Bridge showing various issues on the bridge (Adopted from [MetaInfrastructure.org](https://www.metainfrastructure.org))

In other cases, corrosion caused the collapse of bridges, e.g., the 1985 catastrophic failure of the Ynys-y-Gwas bridge in the UK. In Italy, the collapse of the Polcevera Bridge designed by Professor Riccardo Morandi collapsed leading to 43 fatalities ([Calvi et al, 2018](#); [Domaneschi et al, 2020](#)).

Past studies have focused on exploiting deflection as a damage indicator of ongoing bridge degradation due to stiffness loss caused by tendon corrosion. In ([Ma et al., 2014](#); [Heitner et al., 2019](#); [Vereecken et al., 2020](#)), the methodology consists of updating the estimated levels of corrosion using operational data, i.e. deflection. When discrepancies are observed between predicted deflection values derived from a computational model and real-world measurements, Bayesian inference was used to combine prior knowledge from the initial model with the observed data to update the model parameters that reflect the level of corrosion damage. Nevertheless, this process is computationally intensive and time-consuming, particularly for complex structural problems. Its inherent complexity poses challenges for operators and decision-makers, limiting its practical implementation. While some studies have attempted to detect corrosion-induced damage using ML, they often fail to establish a direct correlation with specific bridge damage states, reducing their effectiveness for structural health monitoring and decision-making. [Ukrainczyk and Ukrainczyk \(2008\)](#) used ANN to

analyse damage from reinforcement corrosion in 11 concrete bridges, incorporating factors such as environmental conditions and concrete properties, assisting in maintenance planning. [Ghiasi et al. \(2022\)](#) applied a k-nearest neighbor (kNN) classifier and Finite Element (FE) model for classifying corrosion-related damage in steel bridges, validated by field test data. [Asadi et al. \(2019\)](#) and [Zhang et al. \(2022\)](#) used ML to interpret Ground Penetrating Radar (GPR) scans, detecting rebar deterioration in concrete bridge decks, while [Mariniello et al. \(2021\)](#) developed the Layout-Aware Extreme Learning Machine (LA-ELM) for detecting tendon malfunctions in prestressed concrete bridges. [Qiao et al. \(2021\)](#) introduced the Expectation Maximum Attention (EMA) module within DenseNet architecture for identifying internal damage, such as exposed steel bars and rebar corrosion.

3.3 Cracking and interpretability

Cracking, whether localised or widespread, is a significant contributor to bridge deck deflection, potentially compromising structural integrity and long-term performance. Cracking in post-tensioned concrete box girder bridges refers to the development of fissures or fractures within the concrete structure ([Podolny, 1985](#)) and is caused by insufficient prestressing and excessive loads ([Erdenebat et al., 2018](#)), or as a result of poor conditions at concrete curing and poor grouting. The presence of cracks indicates a form of distress in the structure and can have a notable impact on the overall behaviour and performance of the bridge, particularly in terms of deflections ([Tong et al., 2016](#)). According to [Gayed and Ghali \(2019\)](#), cracking, particularly under transient loading, leads to increased long-term deflections in concrete slabs due to reduced stiffness at early ages of concrete. [Jin et al. \(2023\)](#) emphasise that cracking in long-span box girder bridges reduces the structure's moment of inertia and shear stiffness, leading to increased deflections, with stress redistribution further complicating the relationship between cracking and deflection. Similarly, [Liu and Xu \(2012\)](#) indicate that cracking weakens the integral rigidity of concrete box girders, preventing effective stress transfer and causing deflections to grow over time. This occurs because the initial stresses distributed along the deck depth are transferred to the prestressing tendons and tensile reinforcement, while the

compressive zone experiences increased compressive stresses, potentially leading to overstressing and triggering long-term creep effects. [Xiang et al. \(2011\)](#) underline that cracking in prestressed concrete box girders alters load distribution and reduces effective stiffness, affecting deflection behaviour under service loads. [Zhang et al. \(2023\)](#) note that cracking affects the overall structural performance by decreasing stiffness and load-carrying capacity, thereby impacting deflection responses. Creep and shrinkage also play a significant role in the development of cracking in concrete structures, including bridge elements ([Baran et al., 2004](#); [Birhane et al., 2020](#)). [Birhane et al. \(2020\)](#) stress the importance of considering cracking in deflection models, as its interaction with creep and shrinkage has a great impact on long-term deflection in prestressed concrete bridges.

Recently, crack detection using ML has gained significant attention in research studies, with a focus on the use of convolutional neural networks (CNNs), support vector machines (SVMs), and transfer learning models ([Firouzi et al., 2013](#); [Ali et al., 2020](#); [Ebenezer et al., 2021](#); [Guzman-Torres et al., 2022](#); [Yang et al., 2022](#); [Chen et al., 2023](#); [Chen et al., 2024](#); [Biswas and Sengupta, 2024](#); [Guo et al., \(2024\)](#), [Gadiraju et al., 2025](#); [Kopiika et al., 2025](#)). For example, [Guo et al. \(2024\)](#) introduced the SE-U-Net model for detecting small cracks, while [Mir et al. \(2022\)](#) applied SVM for crack classification. [Islam et al. \(2022\)](#) proved the ability of the AlexNet model, achieving 99.9% accuracy, for crack detection. Additionally, [Hoshyar et al. \(2023\)](#) introduced SVM-based algorithms to target flexural cracks. Several studies also focused on integrating deep learning models with accessible hardware for real-time applications. [Özcan et al. \(2024\)](#) and [Ravuri and Mantawy \(2024\)](#) attempted using smartphones and UAVs for cost-effective crack detection. [Abubakr et al. \(2024\)](#) and [Cardellicchio et al. \(2023\)](#) used deep learning models like Xception and CNNs to classify cracks among other defects such as corrosion stains, and spalling. [Ji \(2023\)](#) introduced the autonomous system AutoBot for real-time surface crack detection and mapping, while [Bartczak et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Song et al. \(2024\)](#) proposed a UAS-assisted framework using YOLOv8 and Pyramid Scene Parsing Network (PSPNet) for crack detection. Researchers have also addressed the challenge of limited labelled data. For example, [Gao et al. \(2023\)](#) and [Sabarish et al. \(2024\)](#) explored ensemble classifiers like Prototypical

Networks and Radial Basis Function Neural Networks (RBFNN), improving classification accuracy with scarce labelled data.

However, predicting bridge deflections due to concrete cracking and linking them to specific damage states remains an underexplored area, despite the clear benefits of AI and ML methods in this challenging domain. Analysing highly complex, non-linear models that account for all concrete interconnected non-linearities, e.g. cracking, creep, shrinkage etc. is time-consuming and computationally infeasible for every bridge structure. Traditional FEM approaches, despite modern advancements like object-oriented modeling and parallelization techniques ([Bui et al., 2013](#)), still demand significant computational resources for model generation and simulations ([Gamra et al., 2024](#)) complicating bridge assessment and damage identification.

4. Bridging the gap in damage characterisation – traditional methods vs physics-enhanced Machine Learning

Engineers have long been challenged to associate bridge deflections to specific damage mechanisms due to complex interactions and the limits of traditional inspections, which often fail to detect internal damage. Nonlinear and interdependent factors further complicate the issue.

ML can facilitate the analysis of the complex deflection behaviour and link it to damage states, while also generalising knowledge from large datasets and providing rapid, near-real-time predictions ([Hegde and Rokseth, 2020](#)) without the computational burden of FEM ([Ninić and Meschke, 2015](#)).

Beyond bridge engineering, data-driven frameworks have also demonstrated the value of integrating domain-specific knowledge with ML ([Bhowmik et al., 2025](#)).

4.1 Revolutionising Bridge Damage Characterisation through ML Ensembles Informed by Engineering Knowledge, Analysis, and Interpretability

Traditional methods of bridge assessment, as outlined in design and inspection guidelines, are often time-consuming and rely heavily on manual inspections, which are not only subjective but also

challenging to carry out in hard-to-reach areas, making these approaches impractical for assessing large bridge inventories efficiently ([Farahzadi et al., 2025](#)). For instance, the UK's [CS455 \(2022\)](#) outlines a risk-based decision-making process for highway structure assessment, relying on structural reviews and on-site inspections. Similarly, [Caltrans \(2017\)](#) uses visual inspections to classify condition states of prestressed concrete bridge decks, categorising defects from "Good" to "Severe" based on their characteristics. The FHWA's Bridge Management System (BMS) collects condition data, models deterioration, and evaluates maintenance strategies using cost-effectiveness analysis ([FHWA, 2020](#)). These methods require significant resources, are time-consuming and have limited scalability ([Moore et al., 2001](#); [An et al., 2019](#)). Given the vast number of bridges, this approach is not feasible for timely assessments. To address these challenges, more efficient methods are needed that reduce assessment time while improving accuracy. A solution to this challenge is to focus on measurable parameters such as deflection, which can serve as a global metric for rapid damage characterisation. Parametric analysis allows simulations to predict how changes in deflection and material stiffness correlate with varying levels of damage. Once this parametric model is established, ML can automate and enhance the process by learning complex patterns from data, refining damage detection and prediction ([Achillopoulou et al., 2020](#); [Rodrigues et al., 2024](#)). Table 1 compares traditional methods and ML approaches in bridge assessment and damage characterisation. While traditional methods are time-consuming and resource-intensive, ML offers faster, scalable, and more accurate solutions. ML can automate damage detection, adapt to different bridge types, and enable real-time monitoring, making large-scale assessments more efficient.

	Traditional Methods	ML Approaches
Time Efficiency	Time-consuming for detailed inspections and structural analysis in the range of hours (Ninić and Meschke, 2015)	Rapid processing, enabling faster assessments across large numbers of bridges (Wilson et al., 2023)
Data collection and resource requirements	Requires direct, physical inspections which can be time-consuming and costly in terms of both labour and financial resources (Vardanega et al., 2024). Routine inspections in the USA cost \$2.7 billion with an average inspection cost of between \$4500 to	It can utilise both field and simulated data to train models, achieving near 100% prediction accuracy when combining these data sources for bridge damage identification with minimal costs

	\$10,000 per bridge (Liu and Chou, 2023)	compared to traditional methods (Bud et al., 2024)
Scalability	Not scalable for large bridge networks due to resource constraints (Mammeri et al., 2025)	Scalable to assess large numbers of bridges with minimal additional effort (Yuan et al., 2020)
Complexity of analysis	Rely on explicit, predefined models and assumptions about the bridge's structural behaviour (Salehi and Burgueño, 2018)	Learns from data, handling complex and non-linear relationships without explicit assumptions (Salehi and Burgueño, 2018)
Accuracy	Relatively accurate but limited by manual interpretation and human error (Mammeri et al., 2025)	Potentially more accurate when PIML is used (Mammeri et al., 2025)
Adaptability to different bridges	Typically requires separate assessments for each bridge type	Can adapt to different bridge types and conditions through training on diverse datasets (Di Mucci et al., 2024)
Damage detection	Requires manual identification and interpretation of damage indicators (CS455, 2022), (FHWA, 2020)	Automates the detection and classification of bridge damage using trained models (Ghiasi et al., 2022 ; Pentassuglia et al., 2024)
Real-time monitoring	Not suited for real-time assessments	Can enable real-time or frequent monitoring through automated analysis (Freitag et al., 2015)

Table 1: Comparison of traditional methods vs state of the art ML approaches in bridge assessment for damage characterisation

Despite the widespread adoption of ML algorithms across various fields and their proven capabilities in data processing, the "black box" nature of these models continues to be a point of focus for researchers in the engineering field. Traditional ML models are purely data-driven, omitting well-established engineering principles. Recent advancements in PIML ([Dat et al., 2023](#); [Radbakhsh et al., 2023](#); [Balmer et al., 2024](#)) offer a promising solution by embedding known physical laws into the ML training process, specifically in the loss function ([Guo and Fang, 2024](#)). Physics-based constraints act as a form of regularisation, reducing the search space of possible solutions and ensuring physically plausible predictions ([Yamaguchi and Mizutani, 2024](#)). This integration of empirical and theoretical knowledge enhances model reliability, making ML outputs more suitable for engineering decision-making as recent studies in cementitious material modelling have shown ([Anand et al., 2023](#)). PINNs, which emerged at the intersection of ML and computational mathematics, aim to address the black-box limitations of traditional neural networks by enhancing the interpretability of the results.

Meanwhile, data-driven models offer advantages such as speed, predictive accuracy, and scalability. The integration of both approaches can significantly enhance bridge damage characterisation. This concept is illustrated in Figure 5.

Figure 5: Comparison of Model Types for Enhanced Bridge Damage Characterisation: Evaluating the Trade-offs Between Numerical models and Data-Driven Approaches in terms of Interpretability, Speed, Accuracy, and Scalability.

Furthermore, many tasks in civil engineering that require the use of AI tools involve the prediction of multiple dependent attributes (Saini et al., 2025). The problem becomes more complex when these output attributes are interdependent as it is for causes of deflection (Kazantzi et al., 2024). That is, effective prediction of each attribute requires incorporating the values of all other output attributes as additional input. In such cases, traditional ML methods may not be appropriate. To address this type of problem, a two-level cascading ensemble of machine learning methods has been proposed in Izonin et al., (2024), in which the number of ML models at each cascade level corresponds to the number of

dependent attributes to be predicted. At the first cascade level, each output attribute is predicted individually, and these results form a new dataset, which is then analysed at the second level. This approach captures interdependencies between output attributes and provides a solution that is both adequate from a machine learning perspective and more efficient, especially regarding prediction accuracy.

4.2 From deflection to global diagnosis: ML for bridge damage state prediction

Limited research has been conducted on the application of ML to establish a relationship between bridge deflection, driven by multiple interdependent factors, and corresponding damage states. The paper by [Kazantzi et al. \(2024\)](#) introduces a methodology for assessing bridge damage states, focusing on vertical deflections as key indicators of structural integrity, based on the k-Nearest Neighbours (k-NN) supervised algorithm. Simulated scenarios involving prestress loss and stiffness reduction were classified into damage states to train the model, while a test set of similar bridges validated its effectiveness in classifying damage in balanced cantilever bridge structures. [Izonin et al. \(2024\)](#) propose a GRNN-based cascade ensemble model for non-destructive damage assessment in aging bridges, focusing on the impact of tendon losses on vertical deflections. Using numerical simulations, they generated a dataset of damage scenarios and optimized the model with a differential evolution method. The approach, validated on the Polyfytos Bridge, effectively predicts tendon loss patterns despite small datasets and complex interdependencies.

However, these studies exhibit notable limitations in the context of bridge damage characterisation: (i) their scope is restricted to corrosion as the primary damage mechanism, neglecting other critical deterioration processes in concrete bridges such as creep and shrinkage, which are time-dependent phenomena that significantly affect structural deflection and long-term performance, (ii) they fail to correlate measured deflections with model predictions, hindering validation against actual structural behaviour and undermining the reliability of damage assessments, and (iii) their purely data-driven ML approaches disregard underlying physical laws, limiting the interpretability of the results.

To address these gaps, a conceptual framework is proposed by following a systematic four-phase approach for bridge damage characterisation. This approach introduces three key innovations that set it apart from prior research. First, it ensures a precise alignment between measured deflections and model predictions. Second, it offers the first thorough analysis of bridge deflections, taking into account all major deterioration mechanisms such as creep, shrinkage, corrosion, and cracking, and their intricate interactions. Third, it proposes a Physics-Based cascade ensemble ML approach that links deflection patterns to damage states. While the ML architecture itself follows standard practice, the novelty of this work lies in the integration of physics-based deflection simulations with data-driven learning to characterise global bridge damage. This approach bridges the gap between numerical modelling and rapid, interpretable damage assessment. The framework is illustrated in Figure 6 and described in detail below.

Figure 6: ML-based framework for bridge damage assessment using deflection data

The initial phase of data gathering and preprocessing establishes the foundation for the damage assessment framework by systematically collecting and preparing all necessary structural, geometric and environmental data about the specific bridge type under study. Point cloud data, acquired through LiDAR or photogrammetric techniques, undergoes rigorous processing to extract precise displacement measurements at strategically selected bridge locations, particularly focusing on mid-span and support areas where structural responses are most critical. The deflection values derived from the point cloud data represent the total structural displacement, which incorporates the combined effects of time-dependent deformations (creep and shrinkage) and material degradation (corrosion). Following this data acquisition and processing stage, a FEM of the bridge structure is developed to simulate its mechanical behaviour.

The second phase, deflection decomposition, analyses the measured total deflection by separating it into two distinct dominant contributions:

$$\Delta_{tot} = \Delta_{cs} + \Delta_{co}$$

where:

Δ_{tot} is the total measured deflection

Δ_{cs} represents the deflection due to creep and shrinkage

Δ_{co} represents the deflection due to corrosion of the tendons.

The finite element model, constructed to replicate the bridge's original design, serves as the platform for this decomposition. The component of deflection from creep and shrinkage is numerically evaluated and subtracted from the measured total deflection to obtain the residual deflection due to corrosion. The residual deflection is used to optimize the corrosion-related parameters, which subsequently affect the stiffness (Young's modulus) and the creep/shrinkage response in the following iterations. This iterative optimization targets the corrosion-induced deflection component and quantifies the corresponding prestress loss in the tendons. A Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO) algorithm can be employed to calibrate the residual deflection component by minimising the

difference between measured and simulated deflections. This process is repeated iteratively until the sum of the two components equals the measured total deflection.

Building upon the updated model, the framework progresses to its third phase, which focuses on developing a comprehensive training dataset and building drift-based fragility functions. The bridge is divided into three zones, and two types of numerical scenarios are developed using the validated model by varying dominant parameters that influence deflection. In Scenario Type 1, the parameters varied are elastic modulus (E), which simulate the loss of structural stiffness due to cracking, concrete age, temperature, and humidity. These variations result in deflection values for each of the three zones, denoted as Δcs_1 , Δcs_2 , and Δcs_3 . In Scenario Type 2, the parameters varied include the elastic modulus (E) and the reduction in diameter for each of the three zones (\emptyset reduction zone 1, zone 2, and zone 3). The resulting deflection values for these zones are represented as Δco_1 , Δco_2 , and Δco_3 . A numerical evaluation of the training sets is carried out for the different scenarios, each representing distinct damage states defined based on engineering judgment. These training sets are constructed to reflect a wide range of conditions by varying the dominant parameters that influence the structural response. To ensure that the training sets are adequate, it is necessary to evaluate their representativeness and coverage. This involves verifying that the datasets span all relevant damage states and parameter combinations that could realistically occur in the structure. Following the evaluation and validation of the training sets, the next step in the methodology involves the use of vertical drift values obtained from the numerical scenarios to define drift-based fragility functions. These functions are developed to enable a global, rapid assessment of the bridge's damage state. Vertical drift, representing the deflection behaviour of the bridge under various parameter combinations, serves as a key indicator of structural performance and potential damage.

In phase four, a fit-for-purpose, two-level Physics-Based Cascade Ensemble ML framework is developed and trained using the two types of training sets defined in earlier stages. The goal is to leverage both physics-based understanding of structural behaviour and data-driven learning to predict bridge damage states with high accuracy and interpretability. For Type 1 scenarios, the model is

designed to take as input the dominant material and environmental parameters affecting structural response—namely, elastic modulus (E), concrete age, temperature, and humidity. The model outputs are the predicted vertical deflections in each of the three bridge zones: Δcs_1 , Δcs_2 , and Δcs_3 . This level captures the relationship between the varying physical conditions and the resulting structural response, informed by the physics of material behaviour and time-dependent effects. For Type 2 scenarios, the cascade continues by using the observed or predicted vertical deflections (Δco_1 , Δco_2 , Δco_3), along with the elastic modulus (E), as inputs. The model then predicts the extent of geometric degradation in each zone, expressed as diameter reductions in zone 1, 2, and 3.

Both models are trained using the previously validated training sets. The cascade ensemble structure allows the first model to inform the second, ensuring consistency and accounting for interdependencies amongst deflection results in different zones of the bridge. Physics-Based constraints and domain knowledge are embedded throughout the model training process to ensure that predictions remain within realistic and physically feasible ranges, enhancing interpretability of the results compared to prior research.

5. Conclusions

Despite the importance of bridge deck deflection in damage characterisation and actionable damage state identification, design guidelines and published research have not connected deflection to bridge damage. The authors of this review provided evidence that the reason for this disconnect stems from the complexities inherent in deflection, which is the result of several non-linear and interdependent causes, arguably difficult to quantify. Current adopted methods, such as FEM, despite being robust, are time-consuming and often impractical for real-time bridge damage evaluation. This is because FEM analysis requires extensive computational effort and expertise and is slow to be applied in a dynamic environment where rapid assessments are necessary.

This study bridges knowledge gaps in current bridge damage characterisation practices, particularly the narrow focus on single deterioration mechanisms, the lack of alignment between measured

deflections and model predictions, and the limitations of purely data-driven machine learning approaches. To overcome these shortcomings, a novel, systematic four-phase conceptual framework is proposed for comprehensive and interpretable damage assessment.

The methodology introduces three core innovations as a conceptual framework... First, it rigorously aligns measured deflections from point cloud data with FEM predictions, enhancing model interpretability. Second, it incorporates a holistic analysis of deflection behaviour by accounting for multiple, interacting deterioration mechanisms, namely creep, shrinkage, corrosion, and cracking, offering a more complete understanding of bridge performance over time. Third, it develops a fit-for-purpose Physics-Based Cascade Ensemble Machine Learning model that bridges the gap between data-driven models and physical consistency. This conceptual framework introduces a Physics-Based ML approach that maps deflection patterns to actionable damage states, offering a structured roadmap for future research aimed at improving both the accuracy and interpretability of bridge damage characterisation.

This review highlights the critical role of bridge deck deflection as an indicator of global structural damage, focusing on the need to understand its primary causes for effective maintenance and resilience. A systematic literature review identified major contributors such as creep, shrinkage, tendon corrosion, and cracking. With ageing infrastructure, heavier traffic, and environmental stressors, current assessment methods are increasingly inadequate. ML offers a promising alternative for analysing complex deflection data; however, despite its potential, few studies have used it to link specific causes to bridge damage states.

Future research should focus on the development of comprehensive datasets that cover various bridge types and damage states. This can be achieved through collaborative real-world data-sharing platforms and generation of synthetic data. Furthermore, improving model explainability is crucial for building engineer confidence. This can be achieved through collaboration between engineers and data scientists to create algorithms that clearly connect predictions to the underlying factors driving them.

Integrating real-time monitoring systems that combine advanced data acquisition technologies with ML can facilitate ongoing assessment and swift identification of damage. Finally, regulatory bodies should update guidelines to incorporate ML in bridge assessments, enhancing practitioners' trust in automated systems.

Addressing these challenges and pursuing these directions will significantly enhance bridge damage identification, leading to safer and more resilient infrastructure.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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